

Original Research Article

Prevalence of Restless Leg Syndrome in Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

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Restless legs syndrome (RLS) is a common neurological disorder which is commonly misdiagnosed due to its presentation of signs and symptoms with other diseases including Diabetes, Cardiovascular diseases, migraine etc. RLS may worsen with increasing age, and it is more common in women as compared to men. The objective of this study was to document the prevalence of Restless legs syndrome (RLS) in district Hyderabad Sind. This cross sectional survey was conducted at the Civil hospital Hyderabad of Hyderabad, Sindh, from January 19 to September 19. Data was collected by simple random technique through face to face interview. Written consent was taken from all individuals. All parameters including demographic traits, clinical history, smoking history taken. Blood pressure reading was assessed by mercury sphygmomanometer. All four criteria of RLS assessed according to group of RLS study group. Finally 2117 participants participated in this study, the mean age of males was 45.92 ± 16.95 years and in females it was 41.63 ± 17.35 years. Both SBP and DBP was higher in males than females, (it is basic characteristics of participants) the prevalence of RLS was higher in females compare to females. In this study, we reported the overall prevalence of RLS is 13.4% and in females, it is higher compare to men.

Keywords: RLS Epidemiology, RLS Severity, IRLS, Ekbom's Syndrome, RLS Diagnostic Criteria

INTRODUCTION

In 1865, Sir Thomas Willis an English physician described a syndrome Restless legs syndrome (RLS)/ Ekbom's syndrome, a neurological disorder. RLS is characterized by creeping/crawling feeling and periodic lower limbs. This feeling of creeping/crawling subsides with the movements of legs. Sometimes upper limbs are also affected. These symptoms mostly occur during rest hence causing difficult to sleep. As RLS causing disturb sleep at night, patients of RLS are mostly associated with lower quality of life, sleepiness at daytimes, decreased energy, irritation, fatigue and depression. If underlying cause diagnosed and treated than RLS may subside (Batool-Anwar et al., 2016). In 1995, the international RLS study group defined diagnostic criteria of RLS and further revised in the year of 2003. In 2014, a fifth criteria

for diagnosis of RLS added. However, diagnosis of RLS is mainly on clinical basis and there is no any special laboratory test of biological marker for diagnosis (Santos et al., 2016).

Initially RLS classified as a peripheral neurological disorder, however from last two decades, most of the researchers agree that RLS has origin from the central nervous system. Research indicates the changes in the structures of both peripheral and central nervous system, i.e. an irregular sensory motor integration and increased spinal cord excitability, play a major role in the beginning of symptoms (Lamberti et al., 2019). RLS has significant impacts on the health of patients and contribute major economic burden as compare to chronic disorder. RLS is associated with different conditions including insomnia,

disturbed sleep at night, and increased sleepiness at daytime (Mahmood et al., 2015). Recent Western data, suggest the prevalence of RLS ranges between 7 to 11.5% of adult population and incidence is higher in women compare to men. However, intensity of symptoms tends to increase with advancing of age. People consuming alcohols, smokers and who are using selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors are more likely to develop RLS (Akin et al., 2019).

The objective of this study to document the prevalence of restless leg syndrome in district Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

After approval from Ethical Review Board A cross sectional study from January 2019 to September 2019. Subjects aged eighteen years and above included while subjects suffering from stroke or having history of weakness of limb, impaired sensation or trauma history, any active disease other than chronic illnesses including diabetes, hypertension, renal and cardiac diseases were excluded. This study was conducted in Civil Hospital Hyderabad, hospital have busy outpatient and inpatient departments. The data collected by final year medical students who were trained for RLS and administering questionnaire. Simple random technique used for data collection. Written consent was taken from all participants. before collecting data. Data collected through structured questionnaire that included demographic traits including personal history, family history, history of illness, smoking history. This self-structured questionnaire also included the four criteria of RLS study group (Allen et al., 2014).

- (1) Desire to move legs, frequently accompanied by discomfort of legs.
- (2) Worsening of symptoms during rest (inactivity)
- (3) Relief from symptoms by movements
- (4) Symptoms disturbing more in evening and night as compare to day times.

Participants who had all these four conditions are considering as patients of RLS. Than the patients were further inquired about the severity of symptoms, sleep pattern/ Sleep disturbance. However, severities of symptoms categorized into four categories: mild, moderate, Severe and very severe.

The collected data analyzed on SPSS 17.0 versions. The qualitative variables expressed as percentage and quantitative variables were expressed mean \pm SD. A P value <0.05 considered as a statistically significant.

RESULTS

Out of 2973 participants, 2117 participants fulfilled all four IRLSSG diagnostic criteria for RLS, with response rate of

71.20%. Table no 01, describes the basic characteristics of all participants. The mean age of male, participants were 45.92 ± 16.95 , mean age of female participants were 41.63 ± 17.35 . However, the mean age of male participants was higher compare to female participants. The mean systolic blood pressure in male participants was 119.3 ± 6.7 mmHg and in female's 116.5 ± 5.3 mmHg, systolic blood pressure is higher in males compare to females and it shows statistically significance. The mean diastolic blood pressure in males were 80.15 ± 4.63 mmHg and in females 77.96 ± 3.34 mmHg, diastolic blood pressure was higher in males compare to females and it shows statistically significance. Basic characteristics of participants that is why written Education standards were also higher in males as compare to females. Smoking habits found higher in males.

Table 2 describes distribution of participants suffering from RLS with different age group, as our result indicates with the increase age in both male and female participants chances of developing RLS increases.

Table 3 according to scale describes by IRLSSG, almost two thirds of participants were reported in mild and moderate category of symptoms. However, the moderate group consisting the largest number of both genders and in severe and very severe categories females reported higher in number.

Almost 37.6% of participants reported symptoms other parts of body, including arms the trunk, or neck, and 59.7% participants had a family history (first-degree relatives) of similar symptoms. All participants have common symptom of sleep disturbance about 93.7%.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we documented the prevalence of RLS in rural and urban population of district Hyderabad, Sindh. We reported the overall prevalence is 13.41%, in females it is 14.94% while in males 11.46%, the prevalence found higher in females compare to males. Similarly Mahmood et al. (2015), reported higher prevalence than our study. The reason may be in our study number of participants was 2117 than 390. However, prevalence of our study is in agreement with other studies (Alangari et al., 2016; Van Oosterhout et al., 2016).

In our study, the prevalence is higher in women compare to men and this finding is consistent in all age groups of our study. Severity of symptoms is higher in women compare to men and in all age group of our study. The cause of this finding is not clear, in our study. However, the reasons might be women are working more and their food is not proper and due to lack of proper diet that might be causing deficiency of hemoglobin and ferritin level, and increased prevalence of anemia in women of developing countries, these may be the contributing factors. However, a study conducted by salma et al. reported that with the increase of age

Table 1. Basic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Male	Female	P value
Mean age	45.92 ± 16.95	41.63 ± 17.35	>0.05
SBP	119.3 ± 6.7 mmHg	116.5 ± 5.3 mmHg	<0.05
DBP	80.15 ± 4.63 mmHg	77.96 ± 3.34mmHg	<0.05
Education			
Masters	37 (3.96%)	10 (0.844%)	
Graduate	51 (5.34%)	19 (1.60%)	
H.Sc	70 (7.50%)	35 (2.95%)	
S.Sc	35 (3.75%)	37 (3.125%)	
Class VIII	99 (10.61%)	45 (3.80%)	
≤ class V	195 (20.90%)	59 (4.98%)	
Uneducated	446 (47.80%)	979 (82.68%)	
Smokers	673 (72.13%)	119 (10.05%)	
Non-smokers	260 (27.86%)	1065 (89.94%)	

*SBP=Systolic Blood Pressure

*DBP=Diastolic Blood Pressure

Table 2. Distribution of Participants according to different Age GroupWise in RLS

Sex	Age Group	Positive	Total
Female	20-30	24 (9.41%)	255
	31-40	25 (11.261%)	222
	41-50	67 (17.63%)	380
	51-60	61 (18.66%)	327
Male	20-30	24 (7.33%)	327
	31-40	27(10.42%)	259
	41-50	31 (14.83%)	209
	51-60	25 (18.11%)	138

Table 3. Distribution of Participants according to Severity of Symptoms in Rest Less Legs Syndrome (RLS)

Sex	Mild	Moderate	Severe	Very severe	Total
Female	30 (16.94%)	79 (44.63%)	54 (30.53%)	14 (7.90%)	177
Male	25 (23.36%)	52 (48.59%)	26 (24.32%)	4 (3.73%)	107
Total	55 (19.366%)	131 (46.126%)	80 (28.169%)	18 (6.338%)	284

prevalence of RLS becomes higher. K Suzuki et al reported that RLS either idiopathic or secondary to systemic diseases including dialysis, anemia, pregnancy and also reported about familial occurrence (Suzuki et al., 2003).

Another study conducted in china reported decrease

prevalence than our study but it is in agreement with the trend of higher prevalence in females and increased prevalence with increase age (Shi et al., 2015). Another study conducted in Saudi Arabia is in disagreement with our finding of higher prevalence in females and also disagree with our finding of higher incidence with

increased age (Wali and Abaalkhail, 2015).

Association of cigarettes smoking with restless legs syndrome is necessary to understand. In our study, cigarette smoking is associated with the prevalence of RLS. This finding is in agreement with other studies 12. In this study, we reported that insomnia found in 93.75% of participants and about 94.76% reported distress during sleep. A clinical review by Guy Leschziner et al reported strong correlation of RLS syndrome with sleep initiation, difficult to maintain sleep, increased arousal from sleep and not a refreshing sleep (Leschziner, 2018).

CONCLUSION

In this study, we found the prevalence of RLS is higher in women compare to men. Furthermore our study, suggests that RLS associated sleep problem might be a major health issue. However, more epidemiological studies are required to establish prevalence rate and systematic associations and severity of RLS in order to decrease the cases.

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